

A LATTICE MODEL TO SHAPE PHILAENUS SPUMARIUS VECTOR AND XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA PAUCA ST53 TRANSMISSION MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

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Philaenus spumarius (Ps) is the main xylem-sap feeder vector of *Xylella fastidiosa pauca* ST53 (XF), the bacterium responsible for the OQDS symptoms, a devastating plant disease now invading the olive orchards of Apulia. Vector control is expected to be the main action to manage insect-borne pathogens and to contain the following diseases.

We suggest tuning the actual IPM (Integrated Pest Management) strategy to manage the transmission events instead of the vector only. Achievements in Aphrophoridae sampling techniques permit to add a physical (mechanical) control action against vectors eggs in IPM as hitherto sketched. A series of subsequent control actions imposed into a restricted time interval decimate juveniles. Only adults acquire XF feeding on infected plants, to infect (primarily), re-infect and super-infect (secondarily) without latency the olives they encounter until the recipient plants hard too much to be accepted. We consider vector IPM during pre-imaginal life for overall population control and adult control in the way we suggest both crucial to prevent and protect the plants from the infections.

The lattice model we present can help to shape IPM by forecasting the effectiveness of adult control actions through the analysis of the way in which the transmission depends on 1) spacing; 2) number, frequency, intensity, and kind of control actions, and 3) vector mobility in open field or greenhouse-like environments.

